

Effect of Aquo-propan-1-ol Solvent Systems on the [H⁺] Ion-Catalysed Hydrolysis of A Heavy Substituted Formate

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ABSTRACT

Enhancement in the numerical values of free energy of activation (ΔG^*) with simultaneous increase in the values of enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) of the reaction, reveals that propan-1-ol acts as entropy controller solvent. The iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction was evaluated to be 322.0 which infers that there is strong and appreciable solvent-solute interaction in aquo-propan-1-ol reaction media.

KEYWORDS: Industrial Agricultural uses, Solvation, Activation Energies, Iso-kinetic Temperature, Solvent-Solute Interaction

INTRODUCTION

Though the solvent effect of various dipolar aprotic solvents like DMSO, DMF, Acetone, etc. has widely been studied on the acid and alkali catalysed solvolysis of simple esters by various kineticists^{1,2}, but the solvent effect of solvent containing primary alcoholic group (protic solvent) on the industrial agricultural and textile uses of the solvolysis product of a secondary heavy formate (Iso-butyl formate) has not been paid even a little attention so far.

Hence, in order to highlight and elaborate the effect of a solvent protic solvent propan-1-ol on the above noted efficiencies of Iso-butyl formate, it has been proposed to study the effect of propan-1-ol on the acid catalysed hydrolysis of iso-butyl formate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvent propan-1-ol of Merck grade and Iso-butyl formate of export quality packed in Switzerland were taken into use. The kinetics of acid catalysed hydrolysis of the ester was studied as usual by adding 0.65 ml of ester in 50 ml of 0.5 M HCl solution. The values of specific rate constants were evaluated by making use of first order rate equation and are tabulated in Table - I. Evaluated values of the two activation energies (Iso-composition E_C and Iso- dielectric E_D), number of water molecules associated with the activated complex and thermodynamic activation parameters have been enlisted in Tables-II, III, IV and V respectively.

Effect of change of [H⁺] ion concentration on the specific rate constants have been mentioned in Table - VI.

Results and Discussion:

From the evaluated values of specific rate constants tabulated in Table - I, which highlight the effect of change in concentration of the organic content of the reaction media on the rate of reaction, it is clear that there is fast decrease followed by slow depletion in the rate of reaction at approx. 22.50 mol% of propan-1-ol in the reaction media. However, with increasing temperature, the effect of solvent propan-1-ol on degree of depletion of the rate is decreased.

Generally, the following two

factors seem to be responsible for depletion in the rate of the reaction in solution, they are:

- (i) decreasing polarity of the medium as changing from polar water to less polar aquo-propan-1-ol medium,
- (ii) lowering of the bulk dielectric constant values of the medium with gradual addition of propan-1-ol to it, and
- (iii) depletion of concentration of H_3O^+ ions of the solution by the organic content of the media due to its basic character (if any).

As propan-1-ol is not basic, so it may not combine with the H^+ or with H_3O^+ ions of the acidic solution of the reaction media.

Thus ignoring the third one only first and second factors are responsible for depletion of the rate.

Such explanations are in support of the theory of Huges & Ingold³ and views of Laidler & Landskroener⁴ and Elsemony et al.⁵ who have predicted that rate of solvolysis reaction decreases with decrease in dielectric constants of the reaction media. In recent years Sunita & Singh et al.⁶ and Rakesh & Singh et al.⁷ have also reported similar explanations for depletion in the rate of solvolysis reaction with increasing concentration of the organic constant of the reaction media.

Solvent effect on Iso-composition activation energy of the Reaction:

From the slope of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $10^3/T$ values, the values of iso-composition activation energy (E_C or E_{exp}) have been calculated and are enlisted in Table - II.

From Table - II, it is clear that values of iso-composition activation energy go on increasing from 94.16 to 129.81 kJ/mol with addition of 20 to 80% of propan-1-ol in the reaction media.

Generally, enhancement in the values of iso-composition activation

energy may be due to either of the following causes:

- (i.) The greater solvation of initial state than the transition state,
- (ii.) The greater desolvation of the transition state than the initial state, and
- (iii.) Simultaneous desolvation and solvation of the transition and the initial state respectively.

Out of these three factors, the third one seems to be applicable in this case and it has also been supported by the increase in the values of entropy of activation with gradual addition of the organic co-solvent propan-1-ol in the reaction media as shown ahead in Table - V. These views are found in support of recently reported facts by K. Sushma¹⁰ and Sinha & Singh et al.⁹.

Solvent Effect on the Iso-dielectric Activation Energy of the Reaction:

From the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_D$ values against $1/T$ ($\log k_D$ values obtained from interpolation of the plots of $\log k$ values against D values) the values of iso-dielectric activation energy have been evaluated and are recorded in Table - III. From this table, it is inferred that E_D values go on decreasing from 125.47 kJ/mol to 97.58 kJ/mol with increasing D values of the reaction media at $D = 50$ and $D = 65$ respectively. As the dielectric constants (D values) of the reaction media decreases with increasing concentration of propan-1-ol in it, hence the trend of depletion in E_D values of the reaction with increasing D values of the aquo-propan-1-ol reaction media is similar to enhancement in E_C values of the reaction with increasing concentration of propan-1-ol in the reaction media. Thus, it may be concluded that depletion in E_D values of the reaction is complimentary to enhancement in its E_C values.

Similar findings and their interpretations for depletion in E_D

values of the reaction with increasing D values of the reaction media have also been reported recently by Sushma & Singh *et al.*¹⁰.

Evaluation of water molecules involved in the formation of transition state and mechanism of the reaction:

The number of water molecules involved in the formation of the transition state has been determined by plotting log k values against log [H₂O] according to the relation proposed by Robertson¹¹:

$$\log k = \log k_0 + n \log [H_2O]$$

where 'n' is the solvation number which tells about the number of water molecules associated with the transition state and also hints about criterion for studying about the mechanism of the reaction. From the plots of log k values against log [H₂O] values, it is clear that at each temperature two intersecting straight lines with positive slopes are obtained and their slope values have been recorded in Table-IV.

From the value of the slopes, as recorded in Table-IV, it is clear that below log [H₂O] value 1.40 (intersection point of the two straight lines) which corresponds to 45.20 % of water in aquo-propan-1-ol media, the values of slopes are decreasing from 0.696 to 0.343 with increase in temperature from 20^o to 40^oC. Similarly, after log [H₂O] value 1.40, i.e., in case of water concentration above 45.20% in the reaction media, the values of slopes decrease from 1.401 to 0.547 with increase in temperature of the reaction from 20^o to 40^oC.

Overall, it may be concluded that when water concentration fall below 45.20 % in the reaction media, the number of water molecules taking part in the formation of activated complex is about half (0.343), but with increasing concentration of water in the reaction media (above 45.20%) the number of

water molecules associated with the activated complex become above 1 and half (1.401).

However, from decreasing number of water molecules from 1.401 to 0.343 associated with the activated complex with increase in temperature from 20^o to 40^oC, it may be inferred in the light of findings of Robertson *et al.*¹² that mechanistic path of the reaction is changed from unimolecular to bimolecular in presence of propan-1-ol in the reaction media.

It has also been concluded that in presence of propan-1-ol in the reaction media at equilibrium the structure of water is changed from its bulky form to dense form.

Such findings, inferences and their explanations have also been reported recently by Ajeet & Singh *et al.*¹³ and Prashansa & Singh *et al.*¹⁴.

Solvent effect on Thermodynamic Activation Parameters of the Reaction:

By using the Absolute Reaction Rate Theory¹⁵ and the famous Wynne-Jones and Eyring¹⁶ equation, the values of three thermodynamic activation parameters namely enthalpy of activation ΔH^* , entropy of activation ΔS^* and the free energy of activation ΔG^* have been evaluated and are recorded in Table - V.

From the data mentioned in Table - V, the interesting feature comes in the light is that out of the three thermodynamic activation parameters, i.e., ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* values, all the three go on increasing with increasing proportion of propan-1-ol in the reaction media.

From the fundamental thermodynamic equation:

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$$

it may be inferred that the simultaneous increase in the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* with enhancement in ΔG^* values is only

possible when the quantitative increase in the values of ΔH^* is greater than that found in ΔS^* and from this, it is concluded that acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate in aquo- propan-1-ol media is enthalpy dominating and entropy controlled one.

The enhancement observed in the values of enthalpy of activation ΔH^* and entropy of activation ΔS^* also supports the fact that the transition state of the reaction is desolvated and the initial state is solvated in the similar way as reported recently also by Hafizee & Singh *et al.*¹⁷ and Sabita & Singh *et al.*¹⁸.

Effect of change of $[H^+]$ ion-concentration on the reaction media on the rate and mechanism of the Reaction:

The effect of change in the acid concentration of the reaction media kinetics of the reaction was studied by changing the concentration of HCl, but the ionic strength of the reaction media was always kept fixed ($\mu = 0.9$). The evaluated values of the specific rate constant at different $[H^+]$ strength of the media has been tabulated in Table - VI.

The value of the slope of straight line plots of $\log k$ versus $\log [H^+]$ was found to be 1.001 which is almost equal to unity and from this, it is inferred on the guidelines of Zucker and Hammett¹⁹ that this hydrolysis follows $A_{AC}2$ mechanism. Similar inferences have also been reported recently by Raghaw & Singh *et al.*²⁰ for the effect of $[H^+]$ ion concentration of the reaction media on the rate and mechanism of the acid catalysed solvolysis reaction.

Evaluation of iso-kinetic temperature and Solvent-solute interaction in aquo-propan-1-ol reaction media:

In the light of Barclay & Butler²¹, relationship between enthalpy and entropy of activation, the value of iso-kinetic temperature of the acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl

formate in aquo-propan-1-ol media has been evaluated from the slopes of the plots of ΔH^* versus ΔS^* . The plot is straight line and its slope value is evaluated to be 322.0.

From the value of iso-kinetic temperature (much above 300), it is concluded that there is a considerable change in the structure of reactants or in the solvent or in both due to appreciable and strong interaction between solvent and solute present in the reaction mixture in the similar way as reported by Leffler²². Recently Sabita & Singh *et al.*¹⁸ have also reported similar findings and explanations for solvent-solute inter-action in the different reaction media.

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Table - I
Specific rate constant values of Acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-Butyl Formate in
water-Propan-1-ol media
 $k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$

Temp in °C	% of Propan-1-ol (v/v)						
	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20°C	78.09	61.82	50.49	30.59	31.67	36.01	19.90
25°C	156.49	122.96	102.49	83.33	70.31	59.05	47.13
30°C	289.13	344.25	207.66	189.22	154.99	133.08	111.38
35°C	524.93	453.00	465.51	365.03	322.85	85.82	247.80
40°C	958.86	882.27	831.57	760.50	671.19	629.36	553.86

Table - II
Values of Iso-composition Activation Energy (E_c or E_{exp}) of the reaction in water-
Propan-1-ol media.

% of Propan-1-ol	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
E_c values in kJ/mol	94.16	101.65	106.13	113.04	118.06	121.72	129.81

Table - III
Values of Iso-Dielectric Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction at desired 'D'
values of water-Propan-1-ol media

D values	D = 25	D = 35	D = 45	D = 55	D = 65
E_D values in kJ/mol	125.17	123.06	114.45	107.38	99.58

Table - IV
Values of the slopes of the plots of log k versus log [H₂O] values at different temperatures

Temperature in °C	Slope - I Where log [H ₂ O] value is below 1.40	Slope - II where log [H ₂ O] value is above 1.40
20°C	0.696	1.401
25°C	0.602	1.277
30°C	0.466	1.020
35°C	0.440	0.848
40°C	0.343	0.547

Table - V
Variation of ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction with mol% of Propan-1-ol in Water-Propan-1-ol media

% of Propan-1-ol	Mol% of Propan-1-ol	ΔH^* in kJ/mol	ΔG^* in kJ/mol at 30°C	ΔS^* in J/K/mol at 30°C
20%	05.66	92.84	77.39	51.00
30%	09.33	98.93	77.81	69.70
40%	13.79	104.08	78.23	85.30
50%	19.35	110.66	78.57	105.91
60%	26.47	116.82	78.96	124.95
70%	35.90	119.23	79.34	133.60
80%	48.98	126.94	79.78	155.70

Table - VI
Effect of [H⁺] on the Specific rate constant values of Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Iso-Butyl Formate in water-Propan-1-ol media at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.9$)

Concentration of Propan-1-ol=20%

(v/v)

Temp 25°C

[H ⁺]	[KCl]	μ	$k \times 10^3$ in min^{-1}	$2 + \log[\text{H}^+]$	$3 + \log k$	Value of the Slope of the Plots of $\log k$ versus $\log [\text{H}^+]$
0.10	0.80	0.90	25.28	1.0000	1.4028	
0.15	0.75	0.90	58.37	1.1761	1.7662	
0.20	0.70	0.90	78.46	1.3010	1.8999	
0.25	0.65	0.90	100.06	1.3979	2.0000	
0.30	0.60	0.90	112.68	1.4771	2.0499	1.001
0.40	0.50	0.90	119.15	1.6021	2.0761	
0.50	0.40	0.90	156.49	1.6990	2.1945	
0.60	0.30	0.90	199.48	1.7782	2.2999	
0.70	0.20	0.90	276.82	1.8451	2.4422	
0.80	0.10	0.90	316.15	1.9030	2.4999	